

SCI-CONF.COM.UA

THE WORLD OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION

**ABSTRACTS OF VII INTERNATIONAL
SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE
FEBRUARY 10-12, 2021**

**LONDON
2021**

THE WORLD OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION

Abstracts of VII International Scientific and Practical Conference

London, United Kingdom

10-12 February 2021

London, United Kingdom

2021

UDC 001.1

The 7th International scientific and practical conference “The world of science and innovation” (February 10-12, 2021) Cognum Publishing House, London, United Kingdom. 2021. 1055 p.

ISBN 978-92-9472-197-6

The recommended citation for this publication is:

Ivanov I. Analysis of the phaunistic composition of Ukraine // The world of science and innovation. Abstracts of the 7th International scientific and practical conference. Cognum Publishing House. London, United Kingdom. 2021. Pp. 21-27. URL: <https://sci-conf.com.ua/vii-mezhdunarodnaya-nauchno-prakticheskaya-konferentsiya-the-world-of-science-and-innovation-10-12-fevralya-2021-goda-london-velikobritaniya-arhiv/>.

Editor

Komarytsky M.L.

Ph.D. in Economics, Associate Professor

Collection of scientific articles published is the scientific and practical publication, which contains scientific articles of students, graduate students, Candidates and Doctors of Sciences, research workers and practitioners from Europe, Ukraine, Russia and from neighbouring countries and beyond. The articles contain the study, reflecting the processes and changes in the structure of modern science. The collection of scientific articles is for students, postgraduate students, doctoral candidates, teachers, researchers, practitioners and people interested in the trends of modern science development.

e-mail: london@sci-conf.com.ua

homepage: <https://sci-conf.com.ua>

©2021 Scientific Publishing Center “Sci-conf.com.ua” ®

©2021 Cognum Publishing House ®

©2021 Authors of the articles

13.	<i>Liubchik V., Chypyl M., Shabanov V. I., Pavliuchenko O. O., Brovarenko S. V.</i>	98
	PRD (PLASTIC RECYCLING DEVICE) - THE DEVICE FOR CONVENIENT AND EFFICIENT PLASTIC RECYCLING.	
14.	<i>Loiuk O., Hritchenko T.</i>	103
	FORMATION OF THE JUNIOR SCHOOLCHILD'S BEHAVIOR CULTURE: ESSENCE AND STRUCTURE.	
15.	<i>Makarenko M. V.</i>	106
	USE OF A BIG DATA IN HEALTHCARE.	
16.	<i>Mammadova Aytan Jeyun kizi</i>	111
	PERSONAL NAMES IN ANCIENT TURKIC WRITTEN MONUMENTS.	
17.	<i>Melnyk A., Peipei Jia, Ruijie Li, Kubrak T., Shyian M., Bobonych V.</i>	114
	IMPACT OF GROWTH REGULATORS ON THE YIELD CAPACITY OF BROWN MUSTARD IN UKRAINE.	
18.	<i>Murashka K.</i>	120
	RESULTS OF LOCOREGIONAL RADIOFREQUENCY ABLATION AND SURGICAL RESECTION OF LIVER TUMORS AT THE GOMEL REGIONAL CLINICAL ONCOLOGY CENTER.	
19.	<i>Novykova I. V., Danyliuk N. R., Savchenko V. I., Telegina R. A.</i>	129
	CURRENT STATE OF LOCAL GOVERNMENT IN UKRAINE: PROBLEMS AND DEVELOPMENT PROSPECTS.	
20.	<i>Nozadze K. V., Jishkariani M., Pantskhava E.</i>	132
	ENERGY EFFICIENCY - THE MOST IMPORTANT FACTOR IN INCREASING THE COUNTRY'S ENERGY INDEPENDENCE.	
21.	<i>Ohar A. O.</i>	141
	UKRAINIAN LINGUOCULTURAL IMAGE ZEMLIA.	
22.	<i>Okilova M. A.</i>	151
	SOME INFORMATION ABOUT THE ALISHER NAVOI IN THE "NAFAHAT-UL-UNS" ABDURRAHMAN JAMI AND "RASHAHATI AINI-L-HAYAT" FAKHRUDDIN ALI SAFI.	
23.	<i>Posvistak O. A.</i>	158
	IDEAS OF LIBERTARIANISM IN THE PROGRAM DOCUMENTS OF THE POLITICAL PARTIES OF GERMANY.	
24.	<i>Prykhodko I. V., Datsyshyn D. N.</i>	163
	NON-STANDARD FORMS OF EMPLOYMENT.	
25.	<i>Pryshchepa Ye., Pavlenko O., Tymoshenko A.</i>	166
	DYNAMIC BGP OR OSPF ROUTING?	
26.	<i>Rachenko Ye., Dotsenko N.</i>	172
	SHOULD WE USE ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TO RECRUIT EMPLOYEES IN THE AEROSPACE INDUSTRY?	
27.	<i>Rybchynskyi Ie.</i>	176
	ENSURING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SOCIAL POLICY IN THE CONTEXT OF EUROPEAN INTEGRATION.	

UDC 65.012

**SHOULD WE USE ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TO RECRUIT
EMPLOYEES IN THE AEROSPACE INDUSTRY?**

Rachenko Yelyzaveta

PhD student

Dotsenko Nataliia

PhD, Associate Professor

A.N. Beketov Kharkiv National University
of Urban Economy
Kharkiv, Ukraine

Abstract: This paper proposes a technological idea of how to make the recruitment process easier and faster while utilizing Artificial Intelligence (AI). The model in this paper describes how to make current hiring methods more efficient, especially in the aerospace industry.

Keywords: aerospace, project team, skills, artificial intelligence, recruitment

Introductions. As of now, very few recruiters use artificial intelligence in order to advance their hiring method. Although AI is now being used in different industries such as manufacturing, real estate, retail, and others, this paper shows the benefits of utilizing artificial intelligence during a recruitment process in the field of aerospace industry. Finding the most suitable candidates for any particular job require a lot of time-consuming efforts which can be reduced or even eliminated with the use of AI [1, p. 1138].

Aim. This paper aims to offer an idea for an innovative model of using artificial intelligence to the benefit of any aerospace organization. The model will discuss the benefits which such an organization will acquire if it is to use artificial intelligence during their hiring process. This idea can be used by any company that needs new employees, but it would be especially useful for the organizations in

aerospace industry.

Materials and methods. In this paper, we apply a scientific theoretical approach which focuses on creating models, theories, and hypotheses for a better and a more efficient recruitment process in the aerospace industry. One of the theories thoroughly explored in this publication is that the current system of finding new employees in the aerospace industry can be and is in need of being greatly improved [2, p. 1].

Results and discussion. The model which is proposed in this paper shows the benefits of using artificial intelligence during a recruitment process in the aerospace industry. The first benefit of such AI use is that the offered model will greatly speed up the hiring process [3, p. 1]. The search for candidates can now be conducted quicker because it does not need to be conducted by real humans; the computer can compare the qualifications needed for a potential hire and promptly find the most suitable candidates. The AI model can also scan for potential candidates online on the World Wide Web, meaning that it can find professionals which have not even applied to the job. The model would then identify them as suitable candidates and invite those professionals to apply. In addition, AI can also scan candidates' resumes and immediately know whether or not that certain candidate should be seen or / and interviewed by a recruiter or a member of the human resources department. It is understandable that AI may make some mistakes from time to time which is why it is even more important to conduct more research on the AI model discussed in this paper [4, p. 71].

Another reason why an AI model would work great in the industry is because it can conduct all the interviews. Now, instead of the recruiter spending their time on calling or sitting down with each and every candidate, the AI system can independently conduct any kind of a preliminary interview. The AI model will use a combination of interview analytics and natural language processing (NLP) in order to best analyze the candidate's personality traits and skills. A hidden benefit of AI conducting the interview instead of a human being is that this way there would be no bias and no discrimination towards a potential hire [5, p. 2]. However, the downside

of such an automated interview is that the AI system would generally conduct the interview in a similar way with all the applicants - for instance, asking all of them the same questions. That can be a considerable downside if the candidates' experiences are vastly different. Though, the improvements for this AI are possible and should erase this downside if applied.

A benefit which can be easily overlooked, but certainly not because of its importance, is that the AI model can perform background checks of the candidates. Most major organizations conduct mandatory background checks for all newly hired employees and it is an extremely tedious process that can take up a lot of time, energy, and resources of the human resources department [6, p. 1]. Now with the use of AI, the entire vetting of all candidates can be done automatically which would also reduce the biases as well as provide more privacy for the candidates and newly hired professionals. The AI-powered background check can also confirm the reliability of the references written in favor of the potential candidate. Then, depending on what the background check finds, the AI model can help determine the most appropriate compensation, paid leaves, benefits, and other important values which would otherwise take a lot of time to calculate [7, p. 1]. As a newest development, AI can also offer tests and quizzes to candidates in order to not only check the validity of the background experiences and the strength of their education, but also identify and understand the strength of every particular professional.

Conclusions. The model proposed in this publication explained how artificial intelligence can help the recruitment process, especially in the aerospace industry. It can expedite the hiring process and save the resources and energy of the organization which wishes to acquire new employees. The model can independently search for candidates whether they have already applied or not. It can also conduct all the interviews which would reduce and eventually remove the biases and discrimination sometimes cause by a human factor. The background checks can also be performed by artificial intelligence as the model can vet all the potential candidates and check the reliability of their background experience and education. Overall, after researching the new artificial intelligence model described in this paper the next step

would be to conduct more scientific experiments in order to determine the ideal way to utilize such a system with the purpose of improving the recruitment process in the aerospace industry.

REFERENCES

1. Rachenko, Y. (2021). How a new hire can acquire classified data in aerospace industry. *International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering Technology and Science*, 3(1), 1138-1141, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4485131>
2. Perakovic, D. (2019). Novel approach for detection of IoT generated DDoS traffic. Springer, <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11276-019-02043-1>
3. Ahmad, T. (2020). Social network analysis based localization technique with clustered closeness centrality for 3d wireless sensor networks. *Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute*, <https://www.mdpi.com/2079-9292/9/5/738/pdf>
4. Rachenko, Y. (2020). Enhancing the Efficiency of the Current Method of Establishing Team Members in Aerospace Communications. 4th International Scientific and Practical Conference, pp. 69-72, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4483002>
5. Guest Blogger (April 2020). 7 AMAZING WAYS COMPANIES USE AI TO RECRUIT EMPLOYEES. YOH, <https://www.yoh.com/blog/7-amazing-ways-companies-use-ai-to-recruit-employees>
6. Jesmin, R. (2013). Software Development Techniques for Constructive Information Systems. <https://www.igi-global.com/gateway/chapter/75748>
7. Husár, J. (2019). Implementation of Augmented Reality into the Training and Educational Process in Order to Support Spatial Perception in Technical Documentation. 2019 IEEE 6th International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Applications, <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8715120>